

Sensitive Data Toolkit

Part 2: Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix

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Introduction

The Sensitive Data Expert Group of the Digital Research Alliance of Canada has created a suite of tools for Canadian researchers and those in the research community called the Sensitive Data Toolkit. These tools have been created to help researchers understand how research data are documented and described in the research ethics process, and to address the evolution of research data management (RDM) practices such as data sharing and deposit in the context of existing research ethics frameworks.

This tool, the Human Participant Research Data Risk Matrix, is intended as a training tool and educational reference to help those in the research community, or those working with sensitive data, determine risk level for **human participant** research data and make decisions with respect to their management, deposit, and appropriate access/future use. It is intended for use by any party that either contributes or collects data, or that must be consulted about how the collection and storage of sensitive data affects the ethical standing of the project. This includes research team members, members of research ethics boards (REBs), staff in research ethics or research offices, and community research collaborators. It can also be used as a generic guide for creating an institution-specific risk matrix. Please note that local guidance regarding intersecting issues such as privacy may vary. Be sure to seek out guidance from your institution on these issues as well as on institutional data retention and destruction policies.

Risk, and ensuing probability of harm, can be determined through consideration of three factors:

1. Identifiability of the data at the time of collection. This could involve direct identifiers, or combinations of indirect identifiers. See the De-identification Guidance in this toolkit for a more thorough discussion.
2. Identifiability of the data at the time of deposit. The deposited data may be a transformed version of the data as collected. De-identification and other transformations can reduce the risk-level of a dataset.
3. Vulnerability of the data subjects as individuals or as part of a community or population. Whether a data subject or their communit(ies) is vulnerable in the context of data disclosure depends on the potential of the data, if disclosed, to cause them harm. This might include physical, psychological, emotional, social, or legal harm and intersects with potential vulnerability of the data subject as an individual or as part of a community. In the context of community, harms may be created or exacerbated by the potential for misuse in representation of the community, or in violation of community protocols or sovereignty.

Note that multiple versions of a dataset might exist in the context of a given research project and each will need to be managed according to its risk level. For example, a very common scenario is that raw data may be identifiable and classified as extreme risk, but a de-identified version through transformation and suppression of variables, is reduced to high/medium risk.

This matrix is intended to be used in concert with Part 1 of this toolkit, the [Glossary of Terms for Sensitive Data used for Research Purposes](#). Matrix 1 is intended to help classify the data into a risk-category; this will involve the subjective judgement of the interpreter in the specific context of the research. Note that the interpretation of participant harm should be made considering the most vulnerable participants in the dataset and not the average participant. With the classification determined, matrix 2 provides some suggestions on how data should be treated throughout the research lifecycle.

MATRIX 1: CLASSIFICATION

	Low Risk	Medium Risk	High Risk	Extreme Risk
Risk level definitions	<p>Low risk data: Data which, if disclosed, are unlikely to cause harm to participants. These data may have the following characteristics:</p> <p>Publicly available data where there is no reasonable expectation of privacy, regardless of sensitivity or identifiability.</p> <p>Data collected with no information that could reasonably identify individuals or groups.</p> <p>Data contain no confidential, private, or</p>	<p>Medium risk data: Data which require controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and modification and in most cases are considered confidential. Disclosure, loss, or unauthorized modification of confidential information may result in putting research participants in moderate harm. These data may have the following characteristics:</p> <p>All identifiers collected have been stripped so that data have no information that could reasonably</p>	<p>High risk data: Data which require strong controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and/or modification that could result in significant harm. These data may have the following characteristics:</p> <p>Identifiers remain and/or (re)-identification is likely.</p> <p>Data contain confidential, private or sensitive information.</p> <p>Due to these characteristics, data subjects may be vulnerable in the context of the research and it is</p>	<p>Extreme risk data: Data which require the strongest controls against unauthorized disclosure, loss, and/or modification that would almost certainly result in severe harm. These data may have the following characteristics:</p> <p>Identifiers remain and/or (re)-identification is probable.</p> <p>Data contain confidential, private or sensitive information.</p> <p>Due to these characteristics, data subjects are vulnerable in the context of the</p>

	<p>sensitive information.</p> <p>Due to these characteristics, data subjects are not vulnerable in the context of the research and would be quite unlikely to experience harm if a breach were to occur.</p>	<p>identify individuals or groups.</p> <p>Data may contain information originally collected as confidential, private or sensitive.</p> <p>Data are a combination of many publicly available datasets, combined in a novel way, and potentially identifiable.</p> <p>Due to these characteristics, data subjects may or may not be vulnerable in the context of the research. They might experience some harm if a breach were to occur.</p>	<p>likely they would experience significant harm if a breach were to occur.</p>	<p>research and are highly likely to experience significant harm in the event of a security breach.</p> <p>Usage should be restricted. Re-use is often possible only through an agreement (formal or informal) with a custodian, data steward, or data access committee, with no provision for further use or retention.</p>
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NOTE: These risk definitions are not meant to be prescriptive as to the probability of harm occurring in a given category; while they describe risk in terms of disclosure and access controls and risk of re-identification, many tools for calculating risk mathematically exist, particularly the Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario's [De-Identification Guidelines for Structured Data](#), which calculates re-identification risk in terms of data vulnerability and probability of re-identification attack. They serve as general guidelines to allow the reader to determine which category best matches their data, so they can determine what can be done to safeguard the data.

Informed Consent	Consent form should include notification that data will be made available for future unspecified research use (if possible).	Consent form should include notification that de-identified versions of the data will be made available for future unspecified research use (if possible).	Consent form should include notification that data may be made available for future unspecified research use. Request for permission to share and/or deposit data is clearly included in the consent form or process. If possible, provide options regarding areas of future research.	Consent form should include notification that confidentiality will be maintained for as long as the data exist, alongside specific considerations for re-use, or that data will not be shared beyond the research team.
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<p>Data Collection</p>	<p>Publicly available data may be found online or in public archives.</p> <p>Researchers do not know the identities of research participants/data subjects, although confidentiality should not be promised during informed consent.</p> <p>Methods of data collection should not involve direct interaction with research participants. No direct or indirect identifiers are collected.</p>	<p>Researchers may know the identities of research participants/data subjects and may have promised confidentiality through informed consent.</p> <p>Methods for data collection are wide-ranging and may involve direct interaction with research participants.</p> <p>Direct and/or indirect identifiers may be collected.</p>	<p>Researchers may know the identities of research participants/data subjects and may have promised confidentiality through informed consent.</p> <p>Methods for data collection are wide-ranging and may involve direct interaction with research participants.</p> <p>Direct identifiers may or may not be collected, but indirect identifiers collected may be sufficient to render participants identifiable.</p>	<p>Researchers may know the identities of research participants/data subjects and will have promised confidentiality through informed consent.</p> <p>Methods for data collection are wide-ranging and may involve direct interaction with research participants.</p> <p>Direct identifiers may or may not be collected, but indirect identifiers collected may be sufficient to render participants identifiable.</p>
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<p>Data Analysis/Management</p>	<p>No restrictions on the analysis of publicly available data.</p> <p>Data analysis should adhere to any REB-approved protocols.</p>	<p>Direct identifiers should be replaced as soon as possible with a linking code (e.g., pseudonym, alphanumeric code) and the code/codebook separated physically and/or electronically from the master list.</p> <p>Consent forms should be stored separately from research data.</p> <p>Only members of the research team should have access to identifiable data.</p>	<p>Direct identifiers should be replaced as soon as possible, with a linking code, and the code/codebook separated physically and/or electronically from the master list.</p> <p>Consent forms or notes with identifiers should be stored separately from research data.</p> <p>Consider recoding indirect identifiers where this won't interfere with the analysis of the data.</p> <p>Data should not be accessed/analyzed in a public space where others could see data on a device or by other means.</p>	<p>Direct identifiers must be deleted or replaced as soon as possible, with a linking code, and separated physically and/or electronically from the master list.</p> <p>Consent forms or notes with identifiers shall be stored separately from research data.</p> <p>Consider recoding indirect identifiers where this won't interfere with the analysis of the data.</p> <p>Data shall only be accessed by members of the research team as described in the approved protocol, and access/analysis shall only occur in a secure environment.</p>
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Data Storage (Active Storage) and Security	<p>All storage devices, file sharing, and cloud services are allowed.</p> <p>Specialized backup services should not be necessary.</p>	<p>Identifiable data should be stored on password-protected devices, in appropriate secure locations. If data need to be accessible through the internet, they should be encrypted.</p> <p>Public cloud services should be avoided if possible. If they are to be used, files and access should be password-protected and encrypted.</p> <p>Private cloud services, as supported by the research institution and/or assessed as being secure, may be used.</p>	<p>All data should be stored on password-protected encrypted devices, in appropriate secure locations. If data need to be accessible through the internet, they must be encrypted.</p> <p>Public cloud services should be strictly prohibited.</p> <p>Private cloud services, as supported by the research institution and/or assessed as being secure may be used, if approved by the REB and institutional guidance.</p>	<p>All data should be stored on a centralized, stand-alone computer/site that is both password protected and encrypted, in appropriate secure locations.</p>
<p>NOTE: For all risk levels, data should be backed up in a way that is consistent with their risk level.</p>				

<p>Data Deposit and Access (including secondary use)</p>	<p>Data can be deposited with unrestricted access within a reasonable timeframe, taking into consideration publication of original papers.</p> <p>Secondary data use may or may not require REB approval.</p>	<p>Data from participants/data subjects who opt out must be separated from data to be deposited.</p> <p>De-identified data can be deposited with unrestricted access within a responsible timeframe, taking into consideration publication of original papers, the need to replicate research, and to ensure an appropriate shelf-life for reuse of the data.</p> <p>Secondary use of de-identified data requires REB approval.</p>	<p>Data from participants/data subjects who opt out must be separated from data to be deposited.</p> <p>De-identified data can be deposited with restricted access to be evaluated by the data custodian. Data may be separated into sets depending on potential uses that participants have agreed to through informed consent (e.g. use for this study only, only for studies in this subject area, or for any use). Qualitative information provided may be suppressed from deposit if appropriate.</p> <p>Secondary use of de-identified data requires REB approval.</p>	<p>Data should not be deposited anywhere, beyond the direct storage and access needs of the research team.</p>
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Data Retention and Destruction	Data may be retained indefinitely for discovery, access, and archival purposes.	Data may be retained indefinitely for discovery, access, and archival purposes.	Data may be retained indefinitely on a non-internet connected medium, or in a service equipped to store sensitive data, for discovery, access, and archival purposes in accordance with the REB-approved protocol. A protocol for reuse or sharing of the data may be developed and applied to future potential uses of the data. Some data in this category may need to be destroyed.	Data must be destroyed in accordance with the REB-approved protocol.
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Please note that your data retention and destruction procedures will be largely dependent on institutional data retention and destruction policies. When determining whether and for how long you will retain data, and when you will need to destroy data, refer to these policies or seek guidance from your REB.

Note on AI: As a relatively new technology, the ways that AI models use and/or retain data are not always well understood by researchers. In addition, the legal and privacy frameworks surrounding them are not always clear and may vary by jurisdiction (which can include both the locations of the service provider and the user of the service). Free AI systems almost always use the data provided by users to refine and train their models; though paid subscriptions also can and do train models on user data. The specifics of whether or not this applies to a system being considered by a research team can be found in its licensing agreement (these are subject to change and should be reviewed periodically). Both free and

paid systems keep records of queries which may disclose sensitive information if they were to become public, and use of these services should be thought of in the same way as depositing anything that is queried to a corporate cloud.

Due to the variety of tools and the pace of evolution of services and the future potential for a multitude of locally trained and managed AI systems, we have not created a matrix-style guidance for AI or LLM tools. Generally, anyone making use of AI tools to clean or analyze sensitive data (**including those that might arise as feature sets in other commercial software**) should be sure to fully understand how the data are being used and stored by the software. It is possible to create and use LLM and AI tools offline on a local system, as an alternative to free online platforms that may harvest and store data. Using these local instances ensures that input data cannot be harvested or stored.

We would like to hear from you. If you have feedback on the Sensitive Data Toolkit, please take 2-3 minutes to complete this form:

https://docs.google.com/forms/d/1XKG_nnvYZAaym-wYJ7ZkURjIbpBRU0idvsjaqkcEHKU/edit